

A REFLECTION ON CHAPTER IV OF THE BRAZILIAN INCLUSION LAW: ADVANCES AND POSSIBILITIES FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

UNA REFLEXIÓN SOBRE EL CAPÍTULO IV DE LA LEY DE INCLUSIÓN BRASILEÑA: AVANCES
Y POSIBILIDADES PARA LA EDUCACIÓN INCLUSIVA

UMA REFLEXÃO DO CAPÍTULO IV DA LEI BRASILEIRA DE INCLUSÃO: AVANÇOS E
POSSIBILIDADES PARA UMA EDUCAÇÃO INCLUSIVA

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Abstract

This study is part of an ongoing Postdoctoral research and aimed to analyze paths built for educational inclusion through the Brazilian Inclusion Law (LBI) in its articles 27, 28 and 30 of chapter IV, which deals with the rights to education of Person with disability (PwD). The research method used was documentary research of legal acts produced in the LBI that refer to the topic addressed. The results indicate that after approximately ten years of progress towards inclusive education, as indicated by the LBI, intensive monitoring, incentive and guidance work is still needed in order to raise awareness among the population and educational institutions to respect and implement everything that is written and required in the LBI. We conclude that a careful look at compliance with the law is necessary, the creation of laws is extremely necessary to guarantee the rights of people with disabilities, as these are not very valid if they are not well disseminated, monitored and discussed. Hard work is needed to publicize and propagate the ideas put forward and ensure that they are properly monitored. However, the legislative advances that Brazil has been making in pursuit of an increasingly inclusive society are already showing positive results in education and society.

Keywords: Brazilian Inclusion Law; Inclusive Education; Equity.

Resumen

Este estudio es parte de una investigación Postdoctoral en curso y tuvo como objetivo analizar los caminos construidos para la inclusión educativa a través de la Ley de Inclusión Brasileña (LBI) en sus artículos 27, 28 y 30 del capítulo IV, que trata de los derechos a la educación de las persona con discapacidad (PcD). El método de investigación utilizado fue la investigación documental de actos jurídicos producidos en la LBI que hagan referencia a la temática abordada. Los resultados indican que después de aproximadamente diez años de avances hacia la educación inclusiva, como lo señala la LBI, aún se necesita un trabajo intensivo de monitoreo, incentivo y orientación para concientizar a la población y a las instituciones educativas para que respeten e implementen todo

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lo escrito y exigido en la LBI. Concluimos que es necesaria una mirada cuidadosa al cumplimiento de la ley, la creación de leyes es sumamente necesaria para garantizar los derechos de las personas con discapacidad, pues estas poco tienen validez si no son bien difundidas, monitoreadas y discutidas. Es necesario trabajar duro para difundir y propagar las ideas planteadas y garantizar que sean supervisadas adecuadamente. Sin embargo, los avances legislativos que Brasil viene realizando en busca de una sociedad cada vez más inclusiva ya están mostrando resultados positivos en la educación y la sociedad.

Palabras clave: Ley de Inclusión Brasileña; Educación inclusiva; Equidad.

Resumo

Este estudo é parte de uma pesquisa em andamento de Pós Doutorado e teve como objetivo analisar caminhos construídos para a inclusão educacional por meio da Lei Brasileira de Inclusão (LBI) nos seus artigos 27, 28 e 30 do capítulo IV que versa sobre os direitos à educação das Pessoas com Deficiência (PcD). O método de pesquisa utilizado foi à pesquisa documental dos atos legais produzidos na LBI que se referem ao tema abordado. Os resultados apontam que após cerca de dez anos de caminho para a educação inclusiva, sinalizados pela LBI, ainda é necessário um intensivo trabalho de fiscalização, de incentivo e de orientações em busca de conscientizar a população e as unidades de ensino para respeitar e fazer acontecer tudo que está escrito e exigido na LBI. Concluimos que é preciso um olhar criterioso ao cumprimento da Lei, a elaboração de leis é extremamente necessária para garantia dos direitos às pessoas com deficiência, pois estas pouco se tornam válidas se não forem bem difundidas, fiscalizadas e discutidas. É necessário, um trabalho árduo de divulgação e propagação das ideias postas e boa fiscalização para cumprimento delas. Mas, os avanços legislativos que o Brasil vem pontuando em busca de uma sociedade cada vez mais inclusiva já estão mostrando resultados positivos na educação e na sociedade.

Palavras-chave: Lei Brasileira de Inclusão; Educação Inclusiva; Equidade.

Introduction

Historically, education of people with special needs (PSN) is a great challenge for teachers and teaching institutes. The promulgation of the Brazilian Federal Constitution (1988) brought a series of social rights that emphasizes the universality to the access of education. Since then, reforms on the educational system aims quality in education for the development of “people with special needs”.

The terminology “people with special needs” were adopted in the Declaration of Salamanca. This document was the result of the Mundial Conference about Special Educational Needs, in 1994, in Spain. This document created new routes for inclusive education and made it notable in local, national and Mundial debates. It created new routes for Special Educational Needs. It also highlighted this topic in local, national and Mundial debates. For now, Special Educational Needs is valuable in all educational modalities (Brazil, 1994). There are laws and legislations about Special Educational Needs. It aims to

give a better environment and care for the students with deficiencies to guarantee his/her access and stay at school. The focus is to fully develop the potential of the person.

In 2015, it was promulgated by Dilma Roussef the Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities (Law nº 13.146/2015) (LIPD), also known as Statute for People with Disabilities. This regulation constitutes an important regulatory point for the respect and protection of the rights of the People with Disabilities in the country.

The Law nº13.146/2015 is connected with the 5º article, caput, of CF/88. It establishes that “all are equal before the law without distinction of any kind”. Both laws emphasize the educational field of people with disabilities. Both laws also note that, in practice, everyone has their right to education guaranteed.

This study reflects upon the Chapter VI of LIPD connected with the challenges of schools and educational workers to guarantee the principle of equality of the 5º chapter, caput I, of CF/88 in which states that everyone has the right to access education.

The right to education, as shown in the art. 27 of Law nº13.146/2015, is a guarantee that every person with disability has the right to education throughout his/her own life. It assures the development of physical, sensorial, intellectual and social abilities of people with disabilities. Although the LIPD secures many advancements, a lot of challenges remain as obstacles to surpassing providing access and stay at schools and the PWD rights.

Even though the right to education is established by law, the mechanisms necessary to ensure effective inclusion in the school environment, conditions for access, staying in school, and effective learning still need to be reviewed, because it is not just about providing or placing a person with a disability in a classroom. It also involves a whole set of actions that are often forgotten (Santos, 2016).

One of the main problems leading to the ineffectiveness of the Law is that it was created to support a general group of people with disabilities. However, each individual should be treated specifically, in the sense that a person with a certain disability has different needs from another. This requires that the support pedagogical actions also be different, because applying the same actions to different people undermines the main goal of the Law, which is to ensure the maximum development of the person with a disability.

In addition to this issue of the homogenization of actions and contrary to the achievements obtained over time, we still have controversial speeches that not only go

against the policies and legislations achieved but also reinforce prejudiced and stigmatizing discourses about people with disabilities, further hindering their development in educational environments.

Fávero (2016) emphasizes that these discourses revisit the outdated view of special education, which associates the education of persons with disabilities with differentiation and segregation, rather than the realization of access to a human right guaranteed to everyone.

In view of the above, we argue that the issue of inclusion in the educational context should be a topic of discussion not only with educational institutions but also across society, so that reflections can be made to build an educational environment that is truly welcoming and inclusive for people with disabilities.

Based on this context, our research question is: What do Articles 27, 28, and 30 of Chapter IV of the LBI state about the educational rights of people with disabilities? To address this research question, our general objective was to analyze the paths established for educational inclusion through the LBI in its Articles 27, 28, and 30 of Chapter IV, which deals with the right to education for PwD. For this purpose, as specific objectives, we propose to reflect on the legal frameworks established in the LBI regarding education and to discuss the limits and possibilities of the Brazilian Inclusion Law in the field of education.

This article is composed of an introduction and four sections. In the first section, we present the theoretical framework, which addresses the historical trajectory of inclusive education in Brazil. The second section covers the methodology used, followed by the third section, which analyzes the information. Finally, in the concluding remarks, we present the conclusions of the theoretical review.

The findings may help stimulate discussions and promote visibility regarding reflections on compliance with the LBI education. We believe that the advancements established by the Law show positive results in education and society.

The path of Inclusive Education in Brazil

Inclusive Education is characterized as a social justice policy that seeks to include students with disabilities. To understand the social policy, we need to understand the path

of this education and of people with disabilities throughout history and recognize that they were victims of a process of total exclusion, where they were considered unworthy of school education.

In historical records from the Middle Ages, we find information that people with disabilities (PwD) were excluded from society and seen as sick and cognitively incapable, which had implications for knowledge. There are also records that people with some disability or mental disorder were persecuted and executed, as their disability was associated with the “presence of the devil within these people”. For more than 200 years, PwD were burned in public squares, hung, drowned, or imprisoned in the dungeons of castles at the time (Silva, 1987).

After this sad period came the segregation of people with disabilities (PwD), which occurred between the late 18th century and the early 19th century. People with disabilities (PwD) were placed in spaces that treated disability as if it were a disease, leading to the emergence of specialized institutions to care for them. The emergence of these specialized institutions gave rise to what we know today as Special Education (Mazotta, 2011).

In the 20th century, we encounter the paradigm of integration, which emerged to advocate for the right of children with disabilities to be included in society and, especially, in the regular education system. However, this integration had to start with the child with a disability making an effort, as the education systems were not obliged to adapt to the needs of these children (Mazotta, 2011).

In the 1990s, new movements emerged that led to the rise of a new educational paradigm, “inclusion”, in the sense of the word meaning to be part of it. In this context, people with disabilities (PwD) were no longer only physically present in the school environment, as the term suggests that they should actively participate in pedagogical experiences, integrate and socialize with other students, and learn according to their potentials and limitations (Mazzotta, 2011).

According to Mazzota (2011), the inclusion movement began to develop strongly in the first 10 years of the 21st century, and the inclusive education model became the expression of school democratization and acceptance of differences, not as an obstacle, but as a characteristic of every human being, since we are diverse.

Still in the 1990s, two important events took place that emphasized the discussion of an education where everyone benefits: the World Conference on Education for All (1990) and the Salamanca Statement (1994). With these events, the principle of inclusive education gained prominence in the education landscape. Although it did not participate in the events, the Brazilian government committed to considering and developing a welcoming school system and introduced the term “inclusion” in official education-related discourse (Ferrari, 2021).

At these conferences, it was agreed that all nations should commit to inclusive education and that the quality of education should be guaranteed to all, regardless of their conditions and differences, ensuring equal opportunities. It is up to the Nation to promote and ensure this right for people with disabilities, making them an integral part of the educational system.

In 1996, the Law of Guidelines and Bases for National Education (LDBEN), Law nº 9493/96, was enacted, regulating public and private education in the country. In its Article 4, Item III, it guarantees specialized educational services for students with disabilities at all levels, stages, and types of education, but with the repetition of the term regulates public and private education in the country. Chapter V of LDBEN is also entirely dedicated to inclusive education, defined as a modality of school education.

At 2001 it was promulgated the Resolution CNE/CEB nº2/2001, which established the National Guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education. This document covers the provision of services for people with disabilities starting in early childhood education, requiring educational institutions to adapt to receive these individuals, both in physical terms and in terms of pedagogical strategies and adaptations (Brazil, 2001). This document represents a major advance for the time, mainly because it includes early childhood education in its scope. In its third article, Resolution CNE/CEB nº 2/2001 introduces the concept of special education, as follows:

Special Education, a type of school education, is understood as an educational process defined by a pedagogical proposals that ensures special educational resources and services, organized institutionally to support, complement, supplement, and, in some cases, replace common educational services in order to guarantee school education and promote the development of the potential of students with special educational needs at all stages and types of basic education (Brazil, 2011).

Another article to be highlighted in this Resolution is Article 16, which establishes the specific termination of students with disabilities when they do not achieve the educational results set forth in LDBEN 9394/96, and are then referred to youth and adult education or vocational education. For Bravo (2020), the reason for the termination of studies for students with disabilities, established by Resolution CNE/CEB No. 2/2001, implies a setback in relation to the rights acquired by people with disabilities, because while it brings advances, such as early childhood education, it regresses in terms of termination.

In 2008, the National Policy on Special Education from the Perspective of Inclusive Education was published, with the aim of ensuring the inclusion of students with disabilities, the target audience of special education, in schools, guaranteeing access, participation, learning, and continuity of regular education at higher levels of education, advocating for the training of teachers for specialized and inclusive care, involving families in this process, and coordinating architectural and political resources to implement this plan (Brazil, 2008).

This document also recognizes the need for a paradigm shift in relation to specialized parallel care, understood as a process that focuses on disability rather than pedagogical aspects, to make it clear that special education is not a clinical process, but rather constitutes the social being of everyone, in interaction with the environment (Brazil, 2008).

In 2009, the Operational Guidelines for Specialized Educational Services in Basic Education were established through Resolution CNE/CEB No. 4/2009. These guidelines provide guidance on the enrollment of people with disabilities in regular classrooms, but also provide for other services, such as the establishment of Specialized Educational Services (AEE) in the public school system or even in philanthropic, community, non-profit, or religious institutions (Brazil, 2009).

In 2014, the National Education Plan (PNE) was drafted, with Law No. 13,005/2014. In its Article 8, Paragraph 1, Item III, it is determined that federal entities will have one year to organize their education plans with goals aimed at ensuring the specific needs of inclusive education, with a view to ensuring inclusion at all levels, stages, and modalities of education (Brazil, 2014).

People with disabilities now have constitutional support with the enactment of the Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities in 2015 (Law No. 13,146/2015), which aims to ensure and promote equal conditions with other people, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by people with disabilities, with a view to their social inclusion. Chapter IV of this Law will be detailed in the results, as it is the subject of this paper.

In 2017, the National Common Core Curriculum (BNCC) was established by Ordinance No. 1,570/2017 of the Ministry of Education (MEC). This document guides and organizes the rights and objectives of schooling in Brazilian basic education, with a direct impact on the school curriculum in all public and private spheres and other school organizations.

When analyzing the BNCC, we noticed that the term Special Education does not appear in the introduction or summary of the document. It appears only twice in the document, but without specific proposals or guidelines for educational practices. The brief, vague references to Inclusive Education are weak and do not receive the necessary attention. We notice a progressive erasure of these discussions, which becomes greater with each version of the Base.

The most recent update regarding specialized and inclusive services in mainstream schools was established in Decree No. 10,502/2020, published by the Ministry of Education, but which has been suspended by the Federal Supreme Court (STF). This decree intended to establish a new policy focused on special education: "equitable, inclusive throughout life" (Brazil, 2020).

The decree provides for the enrollment of people with disabilities in classes and institutions separate from other students. In addition to being a violation of the Federal Constitution, the measure represents a setback of decades in Brazilian education and contradicts several international declarations and national policies. This Decree expressed an attempt to reinforce old paradigms of special education (integration, segregation) by privileging educational services via private initiative, constituting an obstacle in the fight for the rights of persons with disabilities, especially about public education.

Throughout the history of inclusive education, we have seen that this is a social issue and is part of a proposal to transform educational systems. The principle is the legitimization of a more just and egalitarian education for all. In this concept of inclusive education, all people have the right to belong to a single school context, participating

and learning in the community, regardless of their difficulties and limitations (Brazil, 2008). Mitler (2003, p. 25) understands Inclusive Education as follows:

In the field of education, inclusion involves a process of reform and restructuring of schools, with the aim of ensuring that all students have access to the full range of educational and social opportunities offered by the school.

In this vein, education, which aims at the inclusion of people with disabilities, is understood as a task that aims to develop opportunities for everyone to have access to education, supported by teaching resources that respect differences and diversity, promoting the development of knowledge and the inclusion of these students.

Although Paulo Freire's works date from a period prior to the development of Brazilian school inclusion, they are in line with the current concept of inclusion. In his works, Freire highlighted the importance of education in the process of transforming reality, an education that is liberating and no longer oppressive, for the development of critical awareness in individuals. Freire's focus in his works has always been to discuss, among other issues, social minorities, as well as the possibility of a democratic and emancipatory education.

From this brief history of inclusive education, we can see how much the rights of people with disabilities were neglected in the past. We can see that achievements came slowly and laboriously until the creation of the LBI.

Methodology

Our research is a qualitative study, characterized as a documentary analysis. For Gil (2010), qualitative research is characterized as research that seeks to understand a phenomenon in its natural environment. In this type of study, the researcher is the main instrument for obtaining information, being more interested in the process than in the product. In qualitative research, the researcher can take different paths to obtain data, using a variety of procedures and instruments for data collection and analysis.

For Lüdke and André (1986), documentary research is one in which the data obtained comes from documents with the purpose of obtaining the information contained therein. It is a procedure that uses methods and techniques for capturing, understanding,

and analyzing certain documents. In this study, this research strategy allowed us to identify what the LBI values for inclusive education.

To compile the data, we returned to the research question: "What does the LBI say in its articles 27, 28, and 30 of Chapter IV about the rights to education of people with disabilities?" The documentary analysis, based on Bardin (2011), aimed to investigate the guidelines for inclusive education in the context of the LBI.

The analyses were carried out using an interpretative approach. To this end, we outlined a category of analysis: advances and limitations of inclusive education as set out in the LBI.

Results and Discussion

The LBI presents 127 articles that provide conceptual definitions, anchored in the human rights framework and in line with the 2008 Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

This document addresses the guarantees and rights of persons with disabilities in all areas, promotes social inclusion, prohibits the refusal to enroll children and adolescents with disabilities in the education system, and prohibits the charging of additional fees for these students, thus ensuring a comprehensive and inclusive education system at all levels and lifelong learning, so that students with disabilities can achieve "the maximum possible development of their physical, sensory, intellectual, and social talents and abilities, according to their characteristics, interests, and learning needs" (Brazil, 2015).

Advances and challenges of inclusive education set out in the LBI

The 2015 LBI points out the importance of strategies to reinforce the need to minimize existing barriers for people with disabilities, which, as we have already seen, bring about major mechanisms of exclusion, marked by significant obstacles that directly affect their full exercise of citizenship. The law lists ten fundamental rights, among them the right to education.

This law, published in 2015, brought about significant changes to the rights to inclusive education. One of the changes was the concept of how to refer to individuals with

disabilities (Brazil, 2015): currently, they should be referred to as persons with disabilities and no longer as disabled persons or persons with special needs, as they were previously called.

For Santos (2016), these terms give the idea that the individual carries something, as if it were possible to stop carrying it at any time, or that they have special needs. People with disabilities do not want to be treated differently or specially; they have the right to be treated like anyone else. Therefore, there is no need to refer to them as having special needs.

In this sense, it is necessary to (re)think the Brazilian Educational System and modify the discriminatory structure of exclusion of differences. It is necessary to seek a new structure where the focus is on the school as a whole, with inclusive pedagogical actions that consider the potential of students, regardless of whether they have a disability or not.

Ball (2011, p.30) draws attention to issues related to the implementation of public policies, which, in his view, need to be accompanied by careful research and y to understand the "degrees of application" and "room for maneuver" involved. We agree with Ball (2011), as we need to carefully monitor what the LBI values, an important milestone for guaranteeing the rights of people with disabilities, as it has modified some existing laws and added some other necessary points.

Two points that we believe are essential for a truly inclusive education are the removal of barriers, which implies the continuous gathering of information to meet student performance and to plan and set goals, and compliance with the LBI. The other point presupposes greater involvement between the family and the school and between the school and the community, where everyone seeks a quality education. Fávero (2016) emphasizes that quality inclusive education is based on the right of all students to receive an education that meets their basic and learning needs.

Inclusive education opposes all forms of discrimination, and from this perspective, it is necessary for the educational institution to reevaluate all its concepts and seek an education that respects heterogeneity. In Article 1^o this document makes its objective clear: [...] to ensure and [...] promote, under conditions of equality, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by persons with disabilities, with a view to their social inclusion and citizenship (Brazil, 2015). Within the same law, Article 2 considers people with disabilities to be:

[...] those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments which, in interaction with various barriers, may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others (Brasil, 2015).

This understanding brought into the LBI was taken from the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2008), which served as the basis for the LBI and recognizes disability as a concept that is still evolving. According to Santos (2016, p. 3011).

In addition to affirming and being in line with the Convention's concept of persons with disabilities, the text of the LBI raises the issue of barriers as an innovation for the purposes of recognizing and qualifying disability as a restriction on social participation. The LBI not only describes what barriers are but also specifies six main types of barriers (architectural, urban, transportation, communication, technological, and attitudinal) (Santos, 2016, p.3011).

We note in the words of Santos (2016) that despite the advances achieved through legislation, many challenges remain in practice for the legitimization of the proposed goals, including overcoming the various accessibility barriers faced in the daily lives of these individuals.

To overcome these barriers in the classroom, it is necessary that the law be enforced in a cohesive and consistent manner. It is necessary to adapt spaces to the needs of students. There must be a policy of integration and respect for students with disabilities. According to Freire (1996), if discrimination occurs in the school environment, we do not listen to others, and if we do not listen to them, we cannot talk to them. Also, according to Freire, "[...] If I feel superior to someone who is different, no matter who they are, I refuse to listen to them. The different person is not the other who deserves respect but is this or that mistreatable or despicable" (p.45).

As provided for in LDB 9394/96, the educational institution must offer quality education that listens to and respects the rights and citizenship of each student, regardless of their condition. For this to occur, it must provide support, as well as offer a dignified structure for students with disabilities.

The LBI highlights the obligation to use inclusive teaching practices that respect and cater to diversity, providing for the adaptation of teaching methods for students with disabilities. In articles 27, §1 and §2, and 28, item I, the law establishes that educational institutions must adopt practices that value diversity, providing an education that allows for the full development of all. As we can see from the actions set out in the document:

II – improvement of educational systems, aiming to guarantee conditions of access, permanence, participation, and learning, through the provision of accessibility services and resources that eliminate barriers and promote full inclusion;

VIII – participation of students with disabilities and their families in the various activities of the school community, expanding student's functional skills, promoting their autonomy and participation;

XIII – access to higher education and professional and technological education with equal opportunities and conditions as other people;

XIV – inclusion in curriculum content, in higher education and professional technical and technological education courses, of topics related to persons with disabilities in the respective fields of knowledge (Brasil, 2015).

These actions are important for the access, retention, and full learning of people with disabilities at different levels: Basic, Technical, and Higher Education, which demonstrates a concern for the continuity of studies and the encouragement of inclusion. In the items of Article 30, we have the guaranteed preference for persons with disabilities in services and higher education institutions, with the adaptation of materials aimed at accessibility, both in the selection processes and during the course (Brazil, 2015).

In Article 28, III, the term "reasonable services and adaptations" is repeated.

Article 28 – It is incumbent upon the public authorities to ensure, create, develop, implement, encourage, monitor, and evaluate:

[...]

III – na educational Project that institutionalizes specialized educational services, as well as other reasonable services and adaptations, to meet the characteristics of students with disabilities and ensure their full access to the curriculum under conditions of equality, promoting the achievement and exercise of their autonomy (Brazil, 2015).

Curricular assessment adaptations are essential, according to Oliveira and Machado (2009). Schools, as central institutions in the socialization process, must ensure that all students, regardless of whether they are persons with disabilities, are served according to their specific needs, promoting curricular, technological, and methodological adaptations to facilitate learning (Gonçalves; Ferreira, 2021). However, this is a difficult task for institutions that have become complacent with standardization, excluding any form of diversity from their space.

Although there are legislation and guidelines, many educational institutions still face difficulties in effectively implementing the law, either due to a lack of adequate teacher training or insufficient resources, as there is a significant discrepancy between the legislation and the reality in schools (Carvalho, 2005).

Despite the gains for inclusive education brought about by the LBI, the idea of mixed classes is still challenging, both for families and for educators and educational institutions. It is necessary to enable the infrastructure, pedagogical practices, and even simple everyday activities such as going to the bathroom or moving around the school environment. The LBI is the current law that guarantees the right to full inclusion, emphasizing quality and equity, but as noted, there is still a major obstacle to the inclusion of people with disabilities in the current educational situation. Inclusive education requires a paradigm shift in the way schools approach diversity.

The legislation also provides for the existence of people dedicated to special care within schools, but the lack of dialogue within the community creates more fears and difficulties for all parties. Inclusion is not just about ensuring enrollment in school; people with disabilities must be trained to participate in society with autonomy (Santos, 2016).

Although the LBI and several other documents discuss the rights of people with disabilities, we note that little is known about these documents. Public policies, despite guaranteeing various rights, are rarely publicized to reach the people who most need to know about their rights, who are the very users of the rights promoted by the laws.

These policies need to reach the school community so that everyone can know how to deal with people with disabilities. Even though the LBI guarantees the right to education, it is not everywhere that people with disabilities are able to study and stay in school. However, we believe that the recommendations provided for teacher training, for the restructuring and adaptation of pedagogical practices and school infrastructure offer paths to inclusive practices, which can inspire new studies for the inclusion of people with disabilities. Inclusive special education can no longer be seen as a system parallel to regular education, but rather as part of it, as a set of pedagogical resources and support services that facilitate learning for all.

Final Considerations

A careful look at compliance with the law is needed, and the drafting of laws is extremely necessary to guarantee the rights of people with disabilities. LBI promulgates

actions that drive countless movements fighting for people with disabilities. The LBI is of little value if it is not well disseminated, monitored, and discussed. Hard work is needed to disseminate and propagate the ideas put forward and to ensure that they are properly enforced.

The guiding question of this study, what the LBI says in its articles 27, 28, and 30 of chapter IV on the rights to education of persons with disabilities, were answered in different ways. We believe that the advances made in the LBI are the first steps towards guaranteeing the rights of people with disabilities; without this legislation and other regulatory documents, it would be very difficult to include people with disabilities in educational systems.

Intensive monitoring, encouragement, and guidance are still needed to raise awareness among the population and educational institutions to respect and implement everything that is written and required in the LBI. However, we believe that the legislative advances that Brazil has been making in pursuit of an increasingly inclusive society are already showing positive results in education and society.

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